

THE PROCESS OF CIVILIZATION AND SOCIAL CONSCIOUSNESS

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Annotatsiya: In the modern period in the world, especially during the period of fundamental changes in the life of our country, social consciousness and its manifestations, features of social consciousness, its forms, everyday consciousness, customs, traditions, beliefs, theoretical consciousness, a system of ideas, concepts, laws and other forms spirituality, as well as the transformation of each theory and idea into mass consciousness and its characteristics, Social psychology (psyche), Ideology (ideology). Features of the spontaneous formation of social psychology in people, the emergence of legal consciousness along with the state, the introduction of it by the state as a norm of behavior. Legal consciousness is analyzed through its forms and teachings of the peoples of Central Asia.

Kalit so'zlar: Civilization, public consciousness, everyday consciousness, public consciousness, social psychology, ideology, legal consciousness, state, behavior.

The current period is one of the turning points in human history. This feature of the era can be clearly seen in the fundamental changes taking place in the world, especially in the life of our country. To understand the events and processes taking place in the world and in our country, to form the right attitude to them, to evaluate them based on the specific characteristics of the present day, to draw reasonable conclusions from reality, and ultimately to understand the universe and man requires a deep knowledge of social philosophy, which is one of the fields of philosophy. . In order to gain true knowledge about the issue of social consciousness, first of all, it is necessary to pay special attention to the essence and content of the concept of "social philosophy". This concept is sometimes used in the form of "philosophy of society", "social philosophy", "philosophy of man". The concept of "social philosophy" is inextricably linked with the concepts of "sociality", "social phenomenon" and "social process". These concepts represent the processes of events and events in society[1]. It is known that social consciousness and its forms are expressed to a certain extent in any social events and processes. Therefore, determining the role and importance of one or another form of social consciousness in social phenomena plays an important role in the knowledge of the laws of social development. The theoretical analysis of social consciousness helps to understand the decisive role

of spiritual factors in people's practical activities. Consequently, the category of social consciousness is one of the fundamental categories of social philosophy with its own methodological significance. It is important to study social consciousness and its forms of manifestation. The characteristics of social consciousness are manifested through its forms. For example, everyday or ordinary consciousness mainly reflects the relationship to external relations and events of social life, summarizes them. But everyday consciousness cannot go deep into the essence of things and events. The ordinary mind can have erroneous thoughts. This includes customs, traditions, and beliefs. Everyday consciousness is directly connected with the usual activities of each person in production, life, politics and other spheres. Everyday consciousness is created on the basis of people's understanding of daily life needs. 68 Theoretical consciousness plays an important role in understanding the nature of things and events. Theoretical consciousness represents a system of ideas, concepts, laws, and other forms of spirituality. Ideas appear in theoretical form with their essence. They determine the development of society, give impetus to development. introduced, protected and supported by the state, protects the interests of the people. Legal consciousness is manifested in two forms: a) legal consciousness in the form of social psychology gives people an idea of the relationship between legal and illegal, justice and injustice, and between the individual and the state [3]. People evaluate events such as a sense of justice, the need to take action against a crime, duty and responsibility at the level of legal consciousness, and express their attitude to it; c) legal consciousness represents a certain system of legal views: legal theory, doctrine, code, etc. Legal consciousness performs a number of functions in the system of social relations: a) the function of knowing, providing information, spreading enlightenment, assimilation of legal consciousness by a person, individual, etc.; b) evaluation function: the entity evaluates based on certain legal categories, regardless of its interest and purpose. He has a clear idea about "gratitude", "virtue", "goodness", "evil", "benefit", "harm" and others; c) management function: the legal consciousness defines and manages the legal character and behavior of people, as well as their legal relations and needs. Legal consciousness is inextricably linked with all forms of social consciousness, especially with political and moral consciousness. Moral consciousness is a broader concept than legal consciousness. Legal consciousness is also taken into account in the moral evaluation of events and phenomena[4]. World philosophical thinking has made great progress in understanding the essence of man, and various philosophical currents and schools have emerged.

Important changes in life in the process of civilization, the progress achieved in the study of nature on a scientific basis, it is necessary to study the essence of man, society and social consciousness on a scientific basis, and relying on the conclusions of science, it is necessary to strengthen confidence in the elimination of social disasters and rational management of society. Also, Social consciousness is not only in a specific relationship with social existence, but also to strengthen its connection with individual consciousness, and individual consciousness is the consciousness of some people belonging to a certain social group, nation and people, social reality and real existence are reflected in the consciousness of a separate person, subject. It would be appropriate if the research on the characteristics were further strengthened.

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